

Abstract for Program Book

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<p>Abstract</p> <p>Please type your abstract within the borders of the frame with Font Calibri Size 11pt. (not more than 250 words)</p>
<p>Lower efficacy of albendazole against STH infection among Malaysian indigenous community</p> <p align="center">Khir NAIM^{1*}, Nisha MEHRU^{*1}, Woei Yenn TONG¹, Davamani FABIAN²</p> <p>¹ <i>Institute of Medical Science Technology (MESTECH), Universiti Kuala Lumpur (UniKL), A1-1, Jalan TKS 1, Taman Kajang Sentral, Selangor, 43000 Kajang, Selangor, Malaysia</i></p> <p>² <i>School of Health Sciences, International Medical University (IMU), No.126, Jalan Jalil Perkasa 19, Bukit Jalil, 57000, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia</i></p> <p align="center">*mehrunisha@unikl.edu.my (*Corresponding author's email)</p> <p>Background/ Aims: WHO has reported up to 90% of children from poor communities with inadequate hygiene and sanitation prone to any soil transmitted helminths (STHs) infection. In Malaysia, the indigenous community (Orang Asli) are prone to STH infections due to poor living condition and lack of awareness of STHs infection. Previous studies reported that the control of human STH infection relies on preventive chemotherapy using single-dose albendazole. Hence, the objective of this study was to determine the efficacy of single-dose albendazole against STH infections among Orang Asli related to the prevalence and intensity of infections.</p> <p>Methodology: Fecal samples were collected and it were concentrated by floatation technique (using the standard salt-sugar solution). Next, identification of the helminth type and helminth burden of STHs was performed before and after the albendazole treatment.</p>

Results: After one-month post-treatment, the cure rate (CR) for *Trichuris trichiura* and *Ascaris lumbricoides* was found to be 11.6% and 35.0%, respectively. Moreover, there was no heavy infection for both STHs during the post-treatment of albendazole.

Conclusion: This study indicated that a single dose of albendazole showed higher cure rate efficacy in *A. lumbricoides* compared to than *T. trichiura*. However, both species had decreased egg burden post-treatment with albendazole. Future study in recommended in using double albendazole dose to reduce the helminth burden in this community.

Keywords: Efficacy; Albendazole; *Trichuris trichiura*; *Ascaris lumbricoides*; Soil-transmitted helminths